

D2.5: High Level Architecture (first version)

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Abstract

Deliverable D2.5 presents the first version of the High-Level Architecture of RESCALE. It receives inputs from previous deliverables: D2.1 - Use Case Specification (first Version) & D2.3 - Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version), and correlates those findings to showcase an initial version of the architecture to be developed and utilized within the project. This initial process aims to identify architectural components, blocks that provide specific functionalities or services, separation of concerns, interactions, and information flow. These elements will help lay the groundwork for building the RESCALE platform and achieving the project's goals. This deliverable will be followed by D2.6 - High Level Architecture (final version) in Month 23.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
1.1	Document Structure	8
1.2	Purpose of this Document	9
1.3	Intended Audience	9
1.4	Relation to other Work Packages & other Deliverables	10
1.5	Contributions to Project Objectives	11
2	RESCALE Reference Architecture	12
2.1	Methodology	12
2.2	Logical View	12
2.3	Process View	16
2.4	Scenarios View	21
2.5	Technical Requirements & Components Mapping	29
3	RESCALE Modules	31
3.1	Static Code Analysis Module	31
3.2	Dynamic Testing Module	34
3.3	Management Module	39
3.4	Trust Orchestrator	43
3.5	Repositories	46
3.6	Trust Storage	46
3.7	Security Assurance	49
3.8	Dashboard	50
4	Conclusion & Future Steps	55
4.1	Summary of Key Findings	55
4.2	Recommendations for Project's Next Steps	55

List of Figures

1	RESCALE High-level Architecture	14
2	RESCALE Producer Concept	18
3	RESCALE Consumer Concept	20
4	RESCALE End-user concept	21
5	Static Analysis GRiSP.io / Railway Systems	24
6	Dynamic Analysis GRiSP.io / Railway Systems	25
7	Static Analysis	27
8	Dynamic Analysis	28
9	RESCALE State Management	41
10	RESCALE Dashboard	53

List of Tables

1	TR Mapping for Components of Static Code Analysis Module	29
2	TR Mapping for Components of Dynamic Testing Module	29
3	TR Mapping for Components of Management Module	30
4	TR Mapping for Components of Trust Storage	30
5	TR Mapping for Components of Trust Orchestrator	30
6	TR Mapping for Components of Security Assurance	30
7	TR Mapping for Components of Repositories	30
8	TR Mapping for Components of Dashboard	30
9	Static Code Analyzer - Component Information	32
10	Formal Verifier - Component Information	33
11	SSCG Generator - Component Information	34
12	Low-level Hardware Assessment - Component Information	35
13	Dynamic Hardware Analyzer - Component Information	36
14	Dynamic Software Testing - Component information	38
15	DSCG Generator - Component Information	39
16	State Management - Component Information	39
17	Communication Mechanism - Component Information	42
18	Auth / IAM - Component Information	43
19	TBOM Validator - Component Information	44
20	TBOM Generator - Component Information	45
21	RESCALE Repositories - Component Information	46
22	Ledger Adapter - Component Information	47
23	Ledger Infrastructure - Component Information	48
24	Security Assurance - Component Information	50
25	RESCALE Dashboard - Component Information	51

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
API	Application Programming Interface
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
AVT	Advanced Visualisation Toolkit (tool provided by AEGIS)
C	C (the programming language)
CI/CD	Continuous integration/Continuous Deployment
CIA	Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability
CLI	Command Line Interface
DL	Deep Learning
DSCG	Dynamic Supply Chain Component Guarantee
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
HBOM	Hardware Bill of Materials
IAM	Identity Access Management
IoT	Internet of Things
ML	Machine Learning
NVD	National Vulnerability Database
OS	Operating System
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SaaS	Software as a Service
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
SCA	Side Channel Attack
SSCG	Software Supply Chain Graph
SSCG	Static Supply Chain Component Guarantee
TBOM	Trusted Bill of Materials
TR	Technical Requirement
TrustOR	Trust Orchestrator
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to specify the first version of the architecture that will form the RESCALE Platform. This deliverable results from the initial iteration of Task 2.3 “High Level Architecture Specification”. It includes an overview of the conceptual architecture followed by detailed component descriptions. The deliverable is divided into four main sections beyond this executive summary.

Chapter 1 serves as an introduction to the document. It provides information about the document’s purpose, its structure and the audience to which it is mainly addressed. It also includes the relation to other Work Packages (WPs) and Deliverables.

Chapters 2 and 3 address the main subject of the deliverable, the actual architecture. Chapter 2 includes figures and describes the high-level architecture, information flows, component interactions and how the architecture can be applied to the pilot use-cases. Chapter 3 provides a more detailed description of each component that has been introduced.

Chapter 4 summarizes the contents of the deliverable and includes a “Future Steps” section that outlines the ground for subsequent tasks.

1 Introduction

The RESCALE project is dedicated to innovating secure-by-design supply chains, focusing on automating the evaluation of software and hardware components to ensure freedom from vulnerabilities. It aims to establish effective cybersecurity audit procedures and construct secure systems with robust guarantees. RESCALE introduces novel tools and methodologies throughout the supply chain spectrum by systematically analysing and enhancing each layer of computing systems.

This document presents the outcome of the first phase of Task 2.3, “High Level Architecture Specification”. This phase involves gathering all components and tools that are going to be developed within the project and establishing a high-level architecture specification that indicates how their functionalities work in tandem in order to produce the desired outcomes.

1.1 Document Structure

This section outlines the structure of the deliverable, which is divided into several key areas.

- The deliverable begins with the **Introduction**, which provides a high-level overview of the document content and outlines its purpose, intended audience, and structure. It provides easily-digestible, introductory material that should act as the starting point in order for the reader to be introduced to the concepts presented later. It also explains the document’s relationship with other Work Packages and Deliverables within the project.
- The second chapter, **RESCALE Reference Architecture**, introduces the main subject of this deliverable and is divided into three main parts. The first one begins with the **Methodology**, which provides introductory information on how partners collaborated to achieve the results described in this deliverable and outlines the structure of the entire chapter. Then, the second part includes figures and descriptions for the following three different architecture **View** approaches:
 - *Logical View*: This includes the high-level architecture figure. Through this view, the main functionalities provided by the system are illustrated, and the main modules that comprise the system are introduced.
 - *Process View*: The process view presents the dynamic aspects of the system, including the interactions between its main modules and the communications that drive the run-time behaviour of the system. It also includes the different, “conceptual” User Types of RESCALE.
 - *Scenarios View*: This part describes the sequences of interactions between objects and processes from the perspective of the two RESCALE pilots.

In the third part, namely the **Technical Requirements & Components Mapping**, concludes the chapter with a series of tables that come as a result of mapping the Technical Requirements from Deliverable 2.3 (D2.3) to the identified RESCALE Architecture Components.

- Chapter 3 - **RESCALE Modules** discusses the high-level views which contain a more detailed presentation of every component follows, including the Component Functional descriptions, Prerequisites & Dependencies and Interaction & Interfaces.
- Chapter 4 - **Conclusion & Future Steps**, summarizes the contents of the deliverable and includes a “Future Steps” section that sets the groundwork for the work that will follow.

This deliverable concludes with a list of references used throughout the various sections of the document.

1.2 Purpose of this Document

The primary objective of deliverable “D2.5: High Level Architecture (first version)” is to outline the initial version of the high-level architecture for the RESCALE platform. This document aims to provide a clear and structured overview of the system’s architecture, detailing its main components, their interactions, and the overall information flows within the system.

In this first version of the Architecture deliverables we will cover the conceptual overview of the RESCALE platform’s architecture, including diagrams and descriptions of key components and define how these components interact to achieve the system’s objectives. This document does not delve into detailed technical specifications or low-level design aspects, which will be addressed in the subsequent final Architecture deliverable namely “D2.6: High Level Architecture (final version)”.

This document currently provides the initial outputs of work performed via close collaboration and regular on-line meetings between technical partners and pilot providers, from month 4 up until month 8 of the project for **Task 2.3 High Level Architecture Specification**.

The goal of this document is to establish a comprehensive and coherent high-level architectural framework for the RESCALE platform. It aims to guide the development process by providing clear architectural guidelines and ensuring that all stakeholders have a consistent understanding of the system’s structure. This foundational document is crucial for aligning the project’s technical direction and ensuring the successful implementation of the RESCALE platform.

Having a well-defined high-level architecture is essential for the success of the Project. It ensures that all components are designed to work together seamlessly, facilitates efficient communication among stakeholders and provides a roadmap for the development process within WP3 and WP4. By establishing a clear architectural vision, this document helps to mitigate risks, avoid misunderstandings, and ensure that the project remains on track to meet its objectives.

1.3 Intended Audience

This document is publicly available and should be of use to anyone interested in the RESCALE conceptual architecture. The intended audience includes project stakeholders, development teams, technical architects, and other relevant parties who need to understand the high-level structure and organization of the RESCALE platform. This document serves as a foundational

reference for all team members involved in the project, ensuring a shared understanding and alignment on the system's architecture.

1.4 Relation to other Work Packages & other Deliverables

1.4.1 Other Work Packages

Work Package 2 (WP2) is crucial in laying the groundwork for the entire RESCALE platform by establishing the use-cases, technological requirements, and overarching architecture. Each task within WP2 contributes to and relies on other work packages and deliverables, ensuring a cohesive and integrated approach to developing the RESCALE platform.

The high-level architecture developed in Task 2.3 and presented in this deliverable will guide the development and integration activities in WP3, WP4 and WP5. It will ensure that all components and tools work together seamlessly to achieve the desired outcomes. The architecture will also provide a blueprint for implementing the use-cases and testing scenarios continuing with the evaluation that will be specified in WP5, thus ensuring coherence and alignment across the platform.

1.4.2 Other Deliverables

D2.5 - High Level Architecture (first version): This deliverable outlines the initial high-level architecture, detailing how different components interact and function together. It serves as a foundational document for subsequent refinement and detailed architectural work. As described below in more detail, D2.3 provides input to D2.5, and D2.5 along with future work, will provide input to D2.6:

- **D2.3 - Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version):** This deliverable plays a paramount role in informing D2.5 - High Level Architecture (first version). Specifically, section “3. Initial Requirements Specification” within D2.3 provides foundational inputs that shape the technical and architectural decisions outlined in D2.5. In the upcoming section 2.5, Technical Requirements & Components Mapping, we directly reference those requirements from D2.3 and map them to the components of the high-level architecture presented here.
- **D2.6 - High Level Architecture (final version):** This follow-up deliverable will provide the finalized architecture, incorporating feedback and refinements from the initial version, ensuring a robust and comprehensive architectural framework for RESCALE.
- **D5.1 - Trust Orchestrator (first version):** D2.5 lays the foundational blueprint for the RESCALE project's overall system design, detailing the high-level structure and interactions among various components. This will guide the work of integrating the technology components developed in WP3 and WP4 as it is described in Task 5.1 *Trust Orchestrator and Integration of RESCALE Solutions* and will be reported in D5.1.

Two-cycle Approach of Work Package 2:

As described in the Description of Action, the RESCALE Project adopts a two-cycle approach for the tasks of WP2, namely 2.1 - *Pilots Use Cases Specifications*, 2.2 - *Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification* and 2.3 - *High Level Architecture Specification*. With this deliverable, the first cycle of defining Pilot Use-cases (D2.1), their Requirements (D2.3) and an Architecture (D2.5) that will support them, closes. Consequently, D2.5 will also act as a foundational input for the second and final cycle of deliverables from this Work Package, namely:

- D2.2 - Use Case Specification (final version)
- D2.4 - Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (final version)
- D2.6 - High Level Architecture (final version)

1.5 Contributions to Project Objectives

Objective 1: *Design and develop a complete toolbox to audit and increase the security of supply chain based on emerging technologies for both hardware and software modules.*

D2.5 provides the foundational architecture that integrates the various tools needed for comprehensive security auditing. By detailing the high-level architecture, it ensures that both static and dynamic assessment processes are effectively incorporated, allowing for thorough security guarantees for software and hardware components. The architecture presented also supports the crucial aspect of creating and managing the lifecycle of Trusted Bills of Materials (TBOMs), which on one hand are needed for ensuring the accountability and immutability of the security audit records and on the other hand play an important role to the entire supply-chain.

Objective 4: *Demonstrate and validate the effectiveness and accuracy of the proposed solutions in two complementary use cases with the active engagement of several stakeholders accomplishing at the end of the project a TRL4 for the entire platform.*

D2.5 lays the groundwork for the integration and validation of the RESCALE solutions in real-world pilot trials which will be carried out within the framework of Work Package 5 (WP5). By providing a detailed high-level architecture and then mapping it to actual pilot cases (see section: 2.4 Scenarios View), it ensures that the technological framework is in place to support rigorous testing and validation processes in the specified use cases.

2 RESCALE Reference Architecture

2.1 Methodology

In this deliverable, we employ Kruchten’s 4+1 view model [14, 8] of software architecture to structure and articulate the design of the RESCALE platform. This model, proposed by Philippe Kruchten, is a comprehensive approach to describing the architecture of software-intensive systems using five concurrent views, each addressing specific concerns of different stakeholders. The five views are: Logical View, Process View, Physical View, Development View, and the Scenarios (or Use-Cases) View.

Since this is the first version of our deliverable, our primary focus is on the **Logical** and **Process Views**. The Logical View captures the functional requirements of the system by outlining the key components, their responsibilities, and relationships between them. This view is essential for understanding the system’s overall structure and how it satisfies user requirements. On the other hand, the Process View, addresses the dynamic aspects of the system, detailing how the system’s processes interact, their concurrency, and performance characteristics.

Additionally, in section 2.4, we aim to touch upon the **Scenarios View**, which describes the use cases and scenarios that drive the development and verification of the other views. This inclusion helps in validating the architecture by demonstrating how it can support the two pilots of the project. An important note here is that the approach on integrating the RESCALE solutions to a “Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment” (CI/CD) pipeline appearing within this section illustrates our current view on how the architecture could be practically applied to these real-world use cases. However, as the project progresses and the static and dynamic solutions of WP3 are being implemented, more detailed requirements may emerge that may lead to a full update on currently described CI/CD utilization/integration within RESCALE. The final such integration will become more concrete and will be described in the Physical View of the architecture that will be included in the upcoming deliverable D2.6 - High Level Architecture (final version). Finally, this chapter concludes with a series of tables that map every component of the conceptual architecture to Technical Requirements (TRs).

The architecture presented in this document was developed through an iterative process of discussions and workshops with technical partners during the regular WP2 online meetings and the general assembly ones. It will continuously be refined and adapted during the development phases of the project.

2.2 Logical View

The Logical View of the architecture focuses on the functional aspects of the system, illustrating how the various components interact to fulfill the system’s requirements. This view captures the key abstractions and their relationships, presenting a high-level perspective of the system’s structure. The high-level architecture of RESCALE is comprised of several core components, each serving distinct roles within the system. The architecture diagram is depicted in Figure 1.

2.2.1 High-level Architecture Diagram

The high-level architecture diagram has been split into three logical, horizontal parts, as seen in Figure 1, with each part focusing on a RESCALE specific goal.

- *Assessment domain (light yellow)*: This part includes the two main modules providing the two main functionalities of the project: Static Code Analysis [15] and Dynamic Testing [3]. Their goal is to generate the Static Supply Chain Component Guarantee (SSCG), and the Dynamic Supply Chain Component Guarantee (DSCG), respectively.
- *Management domain (light red)*: This part highlights the core functionalities regarding user-interaction and state management. It includes the Dashboard as the primary touch-point for users to interact with the platform, the State Manager which orchestrates the various operations and maintains the state of different processes, and the Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR), which is pivotal in generating and validating the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) [23]. Authentication/Authorization, Identity and Access Management (IAM), and the communication mechanisms are also components of this layer and will facilitate the proper integration of RESCALE components.
- *Security & Trust domain (light blue)*: This part comprises the foundational elements that support the platform's security and trustworthiness. The Trust Storage Ledger component provides a decentralized ledger for recording and verifying TBOM entries, ensuring immutability, transparency and accountability. The Repositories component is where Static Supply Chain Component Guaranties (SSCGs), Dynamic Supply Chain Component Guaranties (DSCGs) and Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) are stored. These three repositories will serve as essential data sources for the TBOM Generator and Validator. Lastly, the Security Assurance module continuously monitors the security posture of the software, triggering updates to the TBOM when new vulnerabilities are detected, thereby maintaining the platform's overall security integrity.

Figure 1: RESCALE High-level Architecture

2.2.2 Overview of Major Components

Assessment domain:

- Static Code Analysis Module:** The Static Code Analysis Module is a crucial part of the RESCALE platform, responsible for scrutinizing the source code of software components to detect potential vulnerabilities and ensure compliance with security standards. Furthermore, it contains the Formal Verifier component that uses symbolic execution to validate software code according to predefined properties. The module leverages advanced machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques to enhance the accuracy of traditional static code analysis [20], significantly reducing false positives. By performing a comprehensive analysis of the codebase without executing the program, the Static Code Analysis Module can identify security flaws, coding errors, and areas requiring improvement early in the development cycle. The goal of this module is to analyze software and produce the Static Supply Chain Component Guarantee (SSCG).

- **Dynamic Testing Module:** The Dynamic Testing Module, another paramount part of the RESCALE architecture, encompasses three primary tasks, each addressing different aspects of runtime security and vulnerability analysis for software and hardware components within the RESCALE platform: Low-level Hardware assessment, Dynamic Hardware Analysis and Dynamic Software Testing. This module integrates these tasks to ensure robust and comprehensive runtime security analysis and aims to produce the Dynamic Supply Chain Component Guarantee (DSCG).

Management domain:

- **Dashboard:** The Dashboard serves as the main entry point to the platform, providing a user-friendly interface for users to efficiently interact with the system. It offers a range of features, including custom monitoring views, event notifications, filtering capabilities and more, in order to assist the project's management and operational capabilities. Based on a User Access Role model, different workflows in the RESCALE infrastructure are invoked.
- **Management Module:** The Management Module within the RESCALE platform serves as the central coordinating entity, ensuring coherent and consistent operation across various system components. It achieves this through a combination of state management, messaging infrastructure, and authentication/IAM functionalities. The module integrates three key components: State Management, Communication Mechanisms, and Auth/IAM.
- **Trust Orchestrator:** The Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR) serves as the binding framework and offers two primary functions: generating and validating the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) for both hardware and software components. The TBOM Generator creates detailed and secure TBOMs by consolidating data from static and dynamic analysis reports, ensuring comprehensive coverage and adherence to specified standards. The TBOM Validator verifies the integrity and currency of existing TBOMs by cross-referencing entries with the blockchain ledger and assessing the latest security statuses. TrustOR also interfaces with a continuous security assessment mechanism to ensure that TBOMs are updated in response to newly discovered vulnerabilities, maintaining an up-to-date security posture for all monitored components. Through these functionalities, TrustOR ensures the reliability, accuracy, and security compliance of the supply chain components within the RESCALE ecosystem.

Security & Trust domain:

- **Trust Storage:** The Trust Storage module provides a secure and trusted storage solution, consisting of two main components: the Ledger Adapter and the Ledger Infrastructure. The Ledger Adapter serves as the interface for external users, facilitating communication between the RESCALE platform and the underlying ledger system. It enables various functionalities, such as TBOM management, through a set of APIs. The Ledger Infrastructure is engineered to provide extensive flexibility, facilitating the integration of various types of digital ledgers like SQL-based databases, distributed NoSQL, and blockchains. The Ledger Infrastructure guarantees the security, integrity, and authenticity of TBOM data by sustaining a decentralized architecture wherein information is

stored in a verifiable and accountable manner. It maintains a decentralized environment where information is stored in a verifiable and accountable manner.

- **Repositories:** This component is designed to store and manage critical artifacts necessary for the platform's operations. It includes three distinct repositories, each dedicated to storing specific types of artifacts: Static Supply Chain Component Guarantees (SSCGs), Dynamic Supply Chain Guarantees (DSCGs), and Trusted Bills of Materials (TBOMs). These repositories ensure the integrity, availability, and confidentiality of the stored artifacts, implementing robust data management and security practices.
- **Security Assurance:** The Security Assurance component is designed to continuously monitor, test, and assess the security posture of the project and its assets in real-time [22]. It utilizes a range of built-in security assessments addressing the principles of Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA) to provide certifiable security assurance assessments. This module ensures that TBOM reports about software or hardware components remain current and valid by monitoring for new vulnerabilities and security issues. When new threats are detected, it triggers an update process.

A more detailed description of each component will continue in Chapter 3 **RESCALE Modules**, including component functionality, dependencies and interactions.

2.3 Process View

2.3.1 RESCALE User Types

The RESCALE solution has identified three main types of distinct user roles by adapting the User Journey paradigm to the practical needs of the project, namely the Producer, the Consumer and the End User.

The first role is that of the Producer. The Producer is primarily a developer role who may develop a product that may be the starting point in a supply chain, such as a library or a module that may be used by Consumers or End Users, or the developed product may have dependencies from existing libraries that other Producers have deployed. The Producer is focusing on the static analysis testing, with the end product, from the viewpoint of the RESCALE framework being the SSCG.

The second role is that of the Consumer. The Consumer is a primarily a tester role with the ultimate goal of generating the DSCG and the TBOM as a next step. The Consumer may or may not have access to the source code of the product under test and will perform dynamic testing in either hardware and/or software. Once all tests have been performed the Consumer will request the generation of the DSCG and then request the generation of the TBOM.

The last role is that of the End User. The End User is the final user in the supply chain, who simply wants to use a product that has been verified by the RESCALE framework. The End User does not perform any development or assessment to the final product. While the RESCALE solution is focusing mostly on developing the tools and methodologies to secure the supply chain, and as such is focusing more on the Producer and Consumer, it is however important to showcase how End Users can utilize the RESCALE framework.

While these roles have different objectives and scope, we expect that within a project's supply chain, a user may have to assume more than one role. For instance, if a development team wants to incorporate an existing library that has SSCG but not a TBOM, the team must first assume the role of the Consumer to create the TBOM and then assume the role of Producer to develop their solution.

The following three subsections provide a flow diagram of each of these three user types that showcases how each one will use the various components of the RESCALE architecture. Similar to figure 1, the colors used in the following three figures, have the following meaning:

- **Black color:** Components, decisions and mandatory portions of the RESCALE flow.
- **Purple color:** Optional portions of the RESCALE flow.
- **Green color:** Data storage and/or Data retrieved/stored to external to the RESCALE solution components.
- **Red color:** Asynchronous notifications from the Security Assurance.

2.3.1.1 Producer

Figure 2: RESCALE Producer Concept

The Producer begins by retrieving all the required open-source or closed-source code, modules or libraries relevant to the developing product from external repositories to the RESCALE platform, along with their respective TBOMs that have been generated by Consumers.

The Producer then logs in to the RESCALE platform and after authorization, proceeds to validate all the gathered TBOMs. The TBOMs are validated through the TBOM validator of the TrustOR using all the relevant information and the data stored in the Ledger.

Once all TBOMs have been validated, the Producer can optionally register the TBOMs to the Security Assurance component in order to asynchronously get notifications when one or more of the employed TBOMs become invalidated.

Once all the above preparatory steps have been concluded, the Producer can request the static analysis tools and start developing the product's code. Once the code is ready, the Producer can perform a dry run of the static analysis, utilizing the downloaded tools and any static analysis services that RESCALE provides and receive the results and initial guidelines.

If the results of the static analysis modules discover any vulnerabilities, the Producer will be required to redevelop the code and redo the dry run of the static analysis until either all vulnerabilities have been found and mitigated or the Producer is satisfied with the results and any remaining vulnerabilities are not relevant.

At this step the Producer may optionally download and use the dynamic analysis tools and services of the RESCALE platform and perform a dry run, in order to verify that no other vulnerabilities were found. It must be noted that this will not generate any DSCG document.

Once the Producer is satisfied, a final static analysis will be performed which will generate the SSCG. The SSCG will be submitted to the RESCALE repositories as well as be given to the Producer, who now can publish the developed product along with the SSCG.

2.3.1.2 Consumer

Figure 3: RESCALE Consumer Concept

The Consumer begins by retrieving a Producer-developed product from external repositories to the RESCALE platform, along with the SSCG as well as all the TBOMs related to the supply chain components used for the product's development.

Once everything has been retrieved, the Consumer then logs in to the RESCALE platform and after authorization, proceeds to validate all the gathered SSCG and TBOMs. The TBOMs are validated through the TBOM validator of the TrustOR using all the relevant information and the data stored in the Ledger.

Once all the above preparatory steps have been concluded, the Consumer can request the dynamic analysis tools and start assessing the product using the downloaded tools as well as using RESCALE's dynamic testing services.

Once all the tests have been concluded, the DSCG will be generated and submitted to RESCALE's repositories. Once the DSCG is ready, the Consumer can request the TBOM to be generated utilizing the SSCG and DSCG to create RESCALE's final output. Once the TBOM is gener-

ated, it will be stored in RESCALE’s repositories and in the Ledger.

2.3.1.3 End User

Figure 4: RESCALE End-user concept

The End User begins by retrieving a product from external repositories to the RESCALE platform, along with its TBOM. Once everything has been retrieved, the End User uses the TBOM validator service of RESCALE’s platform to validate the product’s TBOM. The TBOMs are validated through the TBOM validator of the TrustOR using all the relevant information and the data stored in the Ledger.

The End User then can optionally register the TBOM to the Security Assurance component to asynchronously get notifications when the product’s TBOMs become invalidated.

2.4 Scenarios View

Scenarios View describes the sequences of interactions between objects and processes from the perspective of RESCALE’s two pilots. Within the *4+1 model* approach, these views are used to identify architectural elements, and to illustrate and validate the design of the architecture. They also serve as a starting point for tests of an architecture prototype.

2.4.1 Pilot-1

This paragraph details the user journeys for two major real-world use cases involving the pilot partner “DIPL. PHYS. PEER STRITZINGER GMBH (PST)”. These use cases illustrate how RESCALE integrates into both development and operational phases.

The first use cases is built around the GRiSP.io SaaS platform [12] and the IoT software and hardware used to connect to it. The platform’s primary focus is the orchestration of distributed systems (of IoT devices) in the scope of manufacturing systems. This in particular involves the

mapping of complex models (representing e.g. the logic of a factory line [24]) onto a set of interacting controllers (IoT devices) for machines. In a broader sense GRiSP.io also has a small community of makers which are using the platform for non-commercial projects.

GRiSP [11] is an IoT hardware platform which can be used in combination with GRiSP.io. The GRiSP2 board is the latest iteration of the GRiSP hardware platform. End users are able to put their own software onto GRiSP hardware and manage fleets of GRiSP IoT devices by means of the GRiSP.io SaaS platform, possibly involving their own Erlang applications (e.g. as backend for IoT devices) which can as well be deployed within GRiSP.io. GRiSP application software is packaged together with RTEMS [19], a library operating system created with the unikernel [26] concept in mind for enhanced security and real-time properties. This overall system of SaaS platform, hardware and operating system related components is maintained by PST and was partially developed as part of the CELTIC-NEXT Piccolo [6] project, the EU LightKone [16] project and the Horizon 2020 TeraFlow [17] project.

The software stack of GRiSP.io and GRiSP is based on Erlang [1] and for the sake of interfacing specific hardware components, GRiSP utilises additional C components (Native Implemented Functions). With the exception of manufacturing related software components, all software parts related to GRiSP.io and GRiSP are open-source [9]. GRiSP.io is based on a HTTP framework and several other Erlang dependencies. The core of the GRiSP software stack is the GRiSP Erlang Runtime Library which enables user applications to access the underlying hardware. Further there is a GRiSP component for the connection to GRiSP.io utilising mutual TLS in combination with a cryptoprocessor (Microchip ATECC608B). Another important component is the secure software update mechanism, which enables over-the-air updates of the whole system. A specific test application PST wants to involve is a solar heating control system [10]. These Erlang libraries and applications can be statically and dynamically analyzed. In the scope of the RESCALE user types PST will take on the role as Producer and potentially as a Consumer of above software components. Furthermore, since customers (end users) of GRiSP.io will use their GRiSP boards and orchestrated cloud instances with their own application software (deployed distributed within GRiSP.io and on IoT hardware), PST will offer an interface within GRiSP.io to provide the necessary technical means such that customers can utilise RESCALE infrastructure with low effort in the role of a Producer of their own software and PST could act as Consumer.

Regarding the second use case PST maintains Linux based embedded operating systems based on Buildroot [18] for public railway systems. These operating systems mostly run on passenger information hardware, mostly displays. As those systems are exposed within public infrastructure they are especially prone to attacks and there is a high customer-driven demand of security assurance to prevent those. The software core of these systems is based on Erlang and similar to the first use case, components for interfacing hardware, mutual TLS in combination with cryptoprocessors and secure over-the-air updates are utilised. These software components are closed-source with their dependencies being mostly open-source. In the scope of the RESCALE user types PST will take on the role as Producer and potentially as Consumer of these software components, while the respective railway company is the end user.

While the commercial setting of the use cases is somewhat different, both use cases have in common that primarily Erlang and to a much lower degree C based software is used. PST will provide a CI/CD infrastructure for both use cases which follows the RESCALE process view outlined in 2.3. Figures 5 and 6 depict the high level workflow in the scope of both use cases for static as well as dynamic analysis. Both parts are elaborated on in the following.

2.4.1.1 Static Analysis

The overall process of static analysis could be integrated into a PST-provided CI/CD system. In case of the GRiSP.io use case this system is tightly integrated into the SaaS platform. PST developers can initiate a RESCALE pipeline consisting of multiple jobs which cover the Producer process described in 2.3.1.1. The GRiSP.io customers are enabled to use the CI/CD system through a specific RESCALE interface within GRiSP.io.

First the TBOMs, the structure of which will be defined in D4.1, are validated according to a policy. The pipeline will fail with a report in case the policy is violated. Then the static analysis module is fetched from the RESCALE infrastructure and a configured set of tools with a configured policy of acceptance is executed on the targeted piece of software code. In case the policy is violated (because of critical findings) the static analysis will fail and provide an actionable report. Otherwise the static analysis is successful and produces an SSCG. It is possible to run the pipeline in a dry run mode, meaning that the developer can introspect the SSCG without publishing any data. Otherwise the SSCG is submitted to the RESCALE management module and the tested software is packaged in a way that enables dynamic testing, e.g. a Docker container for GRiSP.io (or parts of it) or a binary image to be flashed onto GRiSP2. D4.1 and D4.4 will define how a secure session can be established with RESCALE infrastructure and how the SSCG will be verified by cryptographic means (for example a client certificate).

2.4.1.2 Dynamic Analysis

The Dynamic Analysis could be integrated into a CI/CD system. Again, in case of the GRiSP.io use case this system is tightly integrated into the SaaS platform. After fetching the SSCG along with the software artefact the dependency TBOMs are validated. Then the dynamic analysis module is fetched and run together with the targeted software artefact (and necessary hardware) in a sandbox environment. Similar to static analysis specific configurations, policies and also a dry run mode can be involved. If the dynamic analysis is successful according to a given policy and the dry run mode is disabled then the TBOM creation or adjustment is requested. Again, it is assumed here that all communication is secured by means of secure identification and data transfer (to be defined in D4.1 and D4.4).

Figure 5: Static Analysis GRiSP.io / Railway Systems

Figure 6: Dynamic Analysis GRI SP.io / Railway Systems

2.4.2 Pilot-2

This section describes how Pilot partner “CHOCOLATE CLOUD APS (CC)” intends to use RESCALE.

SkyFlok [21] uses a microservice-based architecture [25] written in Python, with a few Python and C++ libraries that are built in house. Each microservice is a separate component, with several internal and external dependencies. The 3rd party libraries include web frameworks (e.g. Flask, FastAPI), database access (e.g. PyMySQL, SQLAlchemy), google specific libraries (e.g. google-cloud-datastore, google-cloud-tasks), etc. The microservices together form the SkyFlok platform. The Python and C++ libraries can be statically and dynamically analysed, but only static analysis can be run on SkyFlok microservices as these cannot be started individually. The dynamically testable counterpart of the microservices is the Skyflok platform as a whole. CC developers take on the role of **Producers** of said components, but are also the **Consumers** of the component’s dependencies.

2.4.2.1 Static Analysis

CC uses Bitbucket Pipelines [5] as a CI/CD platform. When a developer pushes a code change to the Git repository, a Bitbucket Pipelines job is created. First, it runs the unit tests for the specific repository. If these succeed, it requests the Static Analysis tools from the TrustOR of RESCALE. It starts the static analysis by passing configuration parameters, like an access token that references and authorizes a specific component previously registered with the RESCALE platform, the SBOM location, the location of the source code, the programming language, etc. RESCALE’s Static Analysis Module can communicate securely with the RESCALE’s TrustOR, notifying it of a session. It loads the source code, analyses it, then generates an SSCG. During active development, it is started in DRY_RUN mode, which means that the SSCG will not be uploaded to the SSCG database, only returned to the CI/CD to be stored as an artifact, and the job finishes at this stage. The Developer can check the report, make changes to the code and trigger a new static analysis if necessary. If the results are acceptable, another CI/CD with Static Analysis is started, this time without DRY_RUN. The Static Analysis Module will upload the SSCG to the RESCALE SSCG database. After that, the software component is packaged into an artifact, which can mean compilation for C++ libraries, bundling to an archive for a Python library, or building a Docker Image for SkyFlok microservices, etc. This artifact is uploaded to a S3 bucket or a private container registry. The RESCALE TrustOR is notified where to download this artifact from for dynamic analysis. The interface definition metadata is also passed at this stage.

Figure 7: Static Analysis

2.4.2.2 Dynamic Analysis by CC Developers as Producers

As part of the development process, CC developers run Dynamic Analysis of the libraries or the SkyFlok platform to check for vulnerabilities before deployment. RESCALE’s TrustOR gathers the necessary metadata from RESCALE’s database and downloads the necessary artifact. The Dynamic Testing Module can analyse the library directly or start the Docker containers of the SkyFlok microservices using Docker Compose to test the SkyFlok platform. At the end, a DSCG is generated. It is started in DRY_RUN mode, so the DSCG should not be stored for further processing, only the report should be returned to the developer. The TBOM generation is also skipped.

Figure 8: Dynamic Analysis

2.4.2.3 Dynamic Analysis by CC Developers or Third Party Consumers and End Users

When a new version of a dependency or the Skyflok platform is deployed, dynamic analysis and TBOM generation is needed. This can be triggered from RESCALE's Dashboard. The process is similar to what is described above. After the DSCG is generated, it is stored in the DSCG database, the owner of the component is notified via email, then a TBOM is generated and stored using the Trust Storage.

2.5 Technical Requirements & Components Mapping

This section presents a series of tables that map each component of the conceptual architecture to the Technical Requirements (TRs) gathered within Task 2.2: "Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification", as reported in Deliverable 2.3: "Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version)". To facilitate understanding, each line in the tables corresponds to an architectural component with the component name listed in the first cell. The second cell contains a list of corresponding TRs referenced by their IDs, as presented in Table 6 of D2.3. To avoid creating one extensive table, we have divided the information into multiple tables, each representing a different component of our architecture. This modular approach aims to enhance readability and clarity for the reader.

Component	Requirements
Static Code Analyzer	TR003, TR004, TR005, TR006, TR007, TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR016, TR017, TR018, TR023, TR024, TR026, TR027, TR029, TR030
Formal Verifier	TR003, TR004, TR005, TR006, TR007, TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR016, TR017, TR018, TR023, TR024, TR026, TR027, TR029, TR030
SSCG Generator	TR003, TR007, TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR016, TR017, TR018, TR030, TR041, TR042, TR043, TR044, TR045, TR046

Table 1: TR Mapping for Components of Static Code Analysis Module

Component	Requirements
Low-level Hardware Assessment	TR047, TR048, TR049, TR050
Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	TR009, TR031, TR032, TR033, TR034, TR035, TR051
Dynamic Software Testing	TR002, TR008, TR051
DSCG Generator	TR002, TR008, TR010, TR011, TR051

Table 2: TR Mapping for Components of Dynamic Testing Module

Component	Requirements
State Management	TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR017, TR018, TR042, TR057
Communication Mechanism	TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR016, TR018
Auth / IAM	TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR016, TR018, TR056

Table 3: TR Mapping for Components of Management Module

Component	Requirements
Ledger Adapter	TR007, TR011, TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR016, TR017, TR018, TR019, TR020
Ledger Infrastructure	TR002, TR005, TR007, TR022, TR023, TR024, TR025, TR026, TR027, TR028, TR029, TR030, TR031, TR032, TR033, TR036, TR037, TR038, TR039, TR040, TR049, TR050, TR051, TR052, TR053, TR054

Table 4: TR Mapping for Components of Trust Storage

Component	Requirements
TBOM Validator	TR001, TR002, TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR018, TR021, TR041, TR045, TR046, TR052
TBOM Generator	TR001, TR002, TR012, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR018, TR021, TR041, TR042, TR043, TR044

Table 5: TR Mapping for Components of Trust Orchestrator

Component	Requirements
Security Assurance	TR001, TR002, TR013, TR014, TR015, TR017, TR018, TR021, TR022, TR046, TR051, TR052, TR053, TR054, TR055, TR057

Table 6: TR Mapping for Components of Security Assurance

Component	Requirements
Repositories	TR021, TR042, TR043, TR044, TR045, TR046, TR051, TR052, TR056

Table 7: TR Mapping for Components of Repositories

Component	Requirements
Dashboard	TR006, TR010, TR014, TR015, TR017, TR018, TR056, TR057

Table 8: TR Mapping for Components of Dashboard

3 RESCALE Modules

3.1 Static Code Analysis Module

The static code analysis module enhances software security and reliability within the supply chain by performing comprehensive, automated analysis of source code [15], byte code [4] and binaries [7] to identify potential vulnerabilities. Supporting multiple programming languages, the module generates detailed reports that highlight security issues, categorizes them by severity, and provides actionable recommendations based on standardization guidelines and vulnerability databases (CVE/CWE). The module contains multiple sub-components (static code analyzers and formal verifiers) which are combined with ML/DL methods to significantly reduce the number of false positive findings. The resulting report of vulnerabilities is then processed by the Static Supply Chain Component Guarantee (SSCG) generator and the resulting SSCG serves as a first building block towards a TBOM. By adhering to industry standards and best practices, the module helps ensure compliance with regulatory requirements.

3.1.1 Static Code Analyzer

Table 9: Static Code Analyzer - Component Information

Name: Static Code Analyzer
Component Functional Description
The Static Code Analyzer is part of RESCALE’s Software Static Code Analysis Module. The Static Code Analyzer component is designed to scrutinize and assess source code or compiled versions of code to identify potential security vulnerabilities, coding flaws or compliance issues without executing the program. The component aims to integrate advanced ML and DL techniques to enhance its analytical capabilities, significantly reducing false positives and improving accuracy in identifying genuine vulnerabilities. The Static Code Analyzer is built for scalability, ensuring it can adapt to diverse coding environments and evolving cybersecurity threats. The Static Code Analyzer will support auditing the C/C++, Python and Erlang [1] programming languages.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
While the actual packaging of the Static Code Analyzer is yet to be decided, the analyzer could be executable within a containerized technology or run as a standalone tool, ensuring easy deployment and execution. It is desirable to be able to run the analyzer without extended privileges. The component supports multiple programming languages, including Erlang, Python, C, and C++, although specific libraries or sub-components for these languages are yet to be identified. Proper configuration is crucial to ensure that the analyzer can ignore certain sets of vulnerabilities or abnormalities according to predefined rules. Users can customize these settings for local tests, but published reports should adhere to project standards. Public vulnerability databases can be taken into account for the actual scanning and reporting.
Interaction & Interfaces
The resulting static code analyzer report is communicated to the SSCG generator, contributing its findings to the overall report of the module. In the CI/CD context, the feedback from the static code analyzer can be integrated as either success or failure statuses, accompanied by brief explanations and summaries. It also interfaces with a configuration management to apply user-defined rules for ignoring specific vulnerabilities and to adhere to project standards for published reports. The output of the static code analyzer needs to be in a machine-readable format, such as JSON or XML. Reports should include detailed information about detected vulnerabilities, severity levels, and relevant code snippets. While the primary output is a local text file, additional tools may be employed to make this information more accessible and easier to digest for human users.

3.1.2 Formal Verifier

Table 10: Formal Verifier - Component Information

Name: Formal Verifier
Component Functional Description
The Formal Verifier is part of the Software Static Code Analysis Module. It includes an intelligent vulnerabilities exposure engine that leverages the principles of symbolic execution [2] to meticulously assess and validate that software components adhere to their predefined properties. This sub-component is designed to intelligently navigate through the software's paths, identifying potential vulnerabilities by examining all possible states the software can attain, thereby ensuring comprehensive coverage and validation against security breaches and logical errors. Complementing this, formal verification techniques specifically adapted for the unique demands of the Erlang ecosystem will be explored in this component.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
The Formal Verifier component could be executable within a containerized technology or run as a standalone tool. The Formal Verifier requires access to the source code and depends on specific formal methods tools and libraries tailored to the programming languages used in the project, which are yet to be identified. Additionally, it necessitates a configuration management to define the properties and specifications that need to be verified, with the exact details depending on the type of formal verification used.
Interaction & interfaces
The Formal Verifier component communicates with a configuration management to obtain the properties and specifications for verification. Upon completing the verification process, it generates detailed, machine-readable (e.g. XML or JSON) reports that can be integrated into the overall report the static code analysis module produces. These reports provide insights into the correctness of the software, highlighting any discrepancies or issues found during the verification process. In the scope of CI/CD it is desirable that the execution of the component ends in a success or failure state.

3.1.3 SSCG Generator

Table 11: SSCG Generator - Component Information

Name: SSCG Generator
Component Functional Description
The Static Supply Chain Component Guarantee (SSCG) generator is a critical component of the RESCALE project, designed to incorporate the results of the Static Code Analysis and the Formal Verifier Modules into an SSCG together with appropriate meta data like executed tests, environment data, configuration and information about the producing entity. The SSCG is signed by cryptographic means and it is possible to validate it according to specific attributes. The SSCG Generator is utilised at the end of the static analysis and a producing entity uses it to generate a SSCG which can be submitted to the RESCALE SSCG Repository.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
For the generation of a SSCG the results of the preceding Static Code Analysis and the Formal Verifier components are required. A format or layout of the content is yet to be identified and will depend heavily on the output of the two other components. Further the cryptographic assurance of SSCG attributes still needs to be developed and is dependent on the overall process that involves the generation of a TBOM (Task 4.1).
Interaction & Interfaces
The SSCG generator processes the result of the Static Code Analysis and the Formal Verifier components as already described. It integrates with a configuration management to apply user-defined parameters and ensure that the content and cryptographic signatures follow certain requirements and guidelines. The resulting machine-readable SSCG is then made available as output of the static analysis component. Tools may also be developed to make an SSCG easier to digest for human users. For ease of use it might make sense to add an upload functionality to the SSCG Generator such that a generated SSCG can be transferred to the SSCG database via the RESCALE management module.

3.2 Dynamic Testing Module

Complementary to the static code analysis module, the RESCALE Dynamic testing module provides the tools and mechanisms to discover security vulnerabilities in hardware/firmware and software components of the supply chain. To address these issues per component (hardware or software), the Dynamic testing module contains multiple dynamic test approaches matching the various component types in the RESCALE supply chain.

More specifically, this module consists of a Low-level Hardware Assessment subcomponents to detect microarchitectural vulnerabilities as well as software vulnerabilities in privileged low-level software, a Dynamic Hardware Analyzer subcomponent to detecting hardware vulnerabilities and data leakages, and a Dynamic Software Testing subcomponent containing various combinations of – specialised ML/DL-driven fuzzers; traditional (yet state-of-the-art) fuzzers; specialized or general-purpose or open-source dynamic testing tools – in order to perform black box or gray box dynamic testing. Finally this module contains the DSCG generator that combines all the output from the rest of the subcomponents.

3.2.1 Low-level Hardware Assessment

Table 12: Low-level Hardware Assessment - Component Information

Name: Low-level Hardware Assessment
Component Functional Description
The Low-level Hardware Assessment component provides solutions for low-level system security testing. Those include solutions to test for micro-architectural vulnerabilities as well as software vulnerabilities in privileged low-level software (e.g., OS). On the micro-architectural vulnerability front, we focus on Spectre-type vulnerabilities, which cannot easily be eradicated by hardware mitigations and require software not to exhibit any vulnerable code patterns or gadgets. On the software vulnerability front, we focus on OS-level vulnerabilities such as double fetches, which cause the kernel to read user data multiple times without proper sanitization and plague commodity operating system kernels across the board.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
There are no specific dependencies on other internal components. For micro-architectural vulnerability assessment, this component only requires the <i>angr</i> binary analysis platform ¹ . For software vulnerability assessment, this component requires a fuzzer supporting the target operating system kernel. The current implementation targets Linux and the <i>syzscaller</i> kernel fuzzer ² .
Interaction & Interfaces
This is a standalone component operating program analysis of a given (OS kernel) program binary. Given an input binary provided by the analyst, the component outputs a report with the attack surface analysis for the intended micro-architectural or software vulnerabilities. Similar to the static code analyzer, this component can integrate seamlessly with CI/CD pipelines, for instance to trigger automated scans at each code change and provide immediate feedback on newly introduced vulnerabilities. The component complements the other components of the dynamic testing module, contributing its findings to the overall report of the module.

3.2.2 Dynamic Hardware Analyzer

Table 13: Dynamic Hardware Analyzer - Component Information

Name: Dynamic Hardware Analyzer
Component Functional Description
<p>The Dynamic Hardware Analyzer focuses on detecting software or hardware implementation based vulnerabilities due to information leakage from the underlined hardware on which a software/hardware IP core is running. For this component the main information leakage is attributed to side channel leakage due to some physical hardware characteristic like dynamic power consumption, electromagnetic emission or timing. Typical targets of hardware leakage vulnerabilities are cryptography IP cores, thus the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer will target this specific type of IP cores with emphasis on cryptography schemes that are at the latest state-of-the-art like standardized post-quantum cryptography schemes. The Dynamic Hardware Analyzer consists of two core modules, the trace collector and the trace analyzer.</p> <p>Trace collector: This module consists of dedicated FPGA hardware devices like the SAKURA X board along with open access collection platforms (e.g., Flexleco v2.0 platform) and/or COTS trace collection systems like the Chipwhisperer lite project devices. Eventually, the trace collection module includes a series of COTS and RESCALE developed trace collection sensors along with the software/firmware to properly collect traces from those sensors. On top of that, the trace collector module takes into account remote side channel attack assessment, i.e. side channel trace leakage from remote multi-tenant FPGAs with a victim cryptography IP core deployed by one of the FPGA tenants. To facilitate trace collection for such attacks, the trace collector include dedicated “attacker” side channel sensors (like ring oscillators or Time-to-Digital Converters) that can be deployed on a remote FPGA target in order to collect victim tenant’s leakage. Finally, the trace collector include all oscilloscope components/plugins that will support the trace collection process.</p> <p>Trace Analyzer: This module performs all the analysis of the trace collector traces in order to discover possible side channel leakage and also perform series of side channel attacks to assess their applicability on such traces for a specific cryptography IP core under test. The trace analyzer consists of several sub-modules starting with a pre-processing library that enables the proper preparation of traces for the actual analysis. Typical functions of this library are trace averaging, trace filtering, trace alignment, trace scaling etc. The processed traces are fed to the actual analysis library that performed nonspecific leakage assessment following the TVLA methodology that can identify possible exploitable leakage on a given cryptography implementation. After the non-specific trace, the side channel attack (SCA) analysis sub-module is utilized in order to perform a “penetration testing” type of assessment on pre-processed traces. Such a process consist in the application of various known SCAs using the collected traces on a cryptography IP core. The SCA library includes implementations of popular attacks on symmetric key cryptography (e.g., AES) but mostly asymmetric cryptography like elliptic curve cryptography. In several cases ML/DL profiling techniques are used for SCAs and novel approaches are sketched for post-quantum cryptography assessment. The outcome of the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer is provided through the trace analyzer module.</p>

Prerequisites & Dependencies

Depending on the level of analysis required for the cryptographic IP Core under test, the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer may operate over black box (with no knowledge of the source code) or gray box conditions (partial knowledge of the source code). As a requirement, the component needs a series of hardware equipment and their associated firmware/software installed on a single or in some cases two different personal computers. Such equipment includes dedicated or PC assisted oscilloscopes, oscilloscope probes, electromagnetic emission probes, amplifiers, specialized FPGA boards like SAKURA X, specialized embedded system boards for trace collection like chipwhisperer lite UFO boards and various electronics for custom trace collection. The system is self-contained and does not rely on another RESCALE component to provide input.

Interaction & Interfaces

The component uses a dedicated front-end with the Command Line Interface (CLI) to handle all collection and analysis operations. There is a dedicated configuration file that needs to be provided along with programming code that defines the experiment to be conducted by the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer as well as the analysis to be performed after trace collection. As part of the Dynamic Testing Module, this component interacts with the DSCG Generator to report hardware related risks and vulnerabilities.

3.2.3 Dynamic Software Testing

Table 14: Dynamic Software Testing - Component information

Name: Dynamic Software Testing
Component Functional description
<p>The Dynamic Software Testing component focuses on detecting potential security issues and vulnerabilities by applying specialized testing (e.g., DAST, pentesting, fuzzing, symbolic/concolic execution, or specific combinations of all such techniques/tools) on dynamically executed part(s) of a running instance/representation of the system/software/device, regardless whether it is represented as a complete black-box or somewhat-transparent gray-box interface. The component at very high level aims to allow a configurable flexibility of which sub-components/tools to activate during a test/validation, and which configuration(s) to apply so that it suits most optimally the system under test. At the same time, the component's functionality aims to explore and demonstrate the application of AI/ML/LLM to drive the effectiveness, efficiency, and coverage of the employed dynamic testing tools and frameworks. For example, AI/ML/LLM could act as artefact-specific sub-component(s) that could be trained and employed to analyze runtime and dynamic testing artefacts (such as log files, strace/ptrace, stack traces, crashdumps, memorydumps, and others) in order to drive the dynamic testing and fuzzing tools. Depending on the tools employed, the type of tests and the types of artefacts, various artefacts-processing-flows will be activated in order to pre-process the artefacts (e.g., raw crashdumps into valuable crash information) for interpretation by the AI/ML/LLM sub-component(s). Besides exploring existing state-of-the-art fuzzing and dynamic testing tools, the research-oriented partners could possibly develop beyond state-of-the-art specialized or existing-but-enhanced tools, and those will be developed in such a manner to be compatible for integration into the Dynamic Software Testing component and the overall Dynamic Testing Module. The existing or developed tools and frameworks are foreseen to be generally highly-modularized by wrapping them into dockerized/containerized instances and exposing microservice-level APIs (e.g., Swagger, OpenAPIs) inline and compatible with the general RESCALE architecture.</p>
Prerequisites & Dependencies
<p>This component, depending on the configurable test target as well as desired reporting output and granularity, may require access to various combinations of the following: configuration files; source code; API definition; pre-built/compiled binaries and executables; running test target's black box interface (e.g., URL, URI, URN); running test target's gray box access (e.g., OS-level runtime and shell/SSH access, filesystem access, logging/audit access, memory dumps and crashdumps access, etc.). Among other things, the Dynamic Software Testing is expected to employ to a certain degree (and potentially contribute back to): QEMU (https://www.qemu.org/) which is a state-of-the-art emulation framework; AFL (https://lcamtuf.coredump.cx/afl/) which is a state-of-the-art fuzzing framework; Evomaster (https://github.com/WebFuzzing/EvoMaster) which is an AI-driven fuzzing tool that generates system level testcases; Schemathesis (https://github.com/schemathesis/schemathesis) which can generate fuzzing vectors based on the API schema of a service; Meta's LLaMA (https://llama.meta.com/) which is a state-of-the-art open-source LLM framework.</p>
Interaction & interfaces
<p>As part of the Dynamic Testing Module, this component interacts with the DSCG Generator to report any potential security issues or vulnerabilities discovered, providing sufficient yet necessary information for the DSCG and TBOM purposes.</p>

3.2.4 DSCG Generator

Table 15: DSCG Generator - Component Information

Name: DSCG Generator
Component Functional Description
The DSCG Generator, as a component of the Dynamic Testing Module, focuses on ensuring the integrity and security of the supply chain involved in hardware and software development. Based on the input from the dynamic testing tools, it produces dynamic guarantees that confirm the security and integrity of supply chain elements. It generates detailed reports and sends them to the DSCG RESCALE repository.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
The functionality of this component depends on the ability of preceding components to properly process binary files for identifying patterns and potential risks.
Interaction & Interfaces
An interface may be needed to display detailed guarantee reports to the user, who gets notified either through the RESCALE dashboard or by reading the DSCG output. The DSCG Generator interacts with other components within the Dynamic Testing Module. Additionally, through the management module, it interacts with the DSCG repository to save the generated dynamic guarantees into the database.

3.3 Management Module

The Management Module serves as the main orchestration pillar within the RESCALE infrastructure, tasked with managing function executions and orchestrating information flow pipelines. It acts as a central hub, receiving inputs from the interconnected system components, while undertaking authentication and validation tasks. Therefore, it handles data exchange requests between internal backend operations and external user requests, orchestrates tasks to ensure processes are executed in the correct sequence and manages dependencies. This module also supports, as a middleware client, the RESCALE Dashboard and translating and executing user requests. The following section provides high level architectural details and interactions for the State Manager, the Auth/IAM and the Communication Mechanisms of the RESCALE ecosystem.

3.3.1 State Management

Table 16: State Management - Component Information

Name: State Management
Component Functional Description

The State Management Module is a central RESCALE component responsible for handling multiple critical functions within the system and ensuring that the flow of the information is preserved. It receives input from all components of the RESCALE ecosystem. Particularly, both static and dynamic analysis modules transmit data outputs to the management module to distribute the data to the rest of the interconnected components like the TrustOR, the RESCALE Repositories or the Ledger Infrastructure. Additionally, it is responsible for handling multiple requests for data exchange among various internal (back-end operations) and external (user requests) system services; thus, it orchestrates various tasks and activities to ensure that processes are executed in the correct sequence and dependencies between tasks are well managed. This ensures that all parts of the system have the necessary information to function correctly. Finally, it serves as a complementary back-end client to the RESCALE Dashboard to efficiently translate and execute user requests to operational RESCALE capabilities. This ensures that user interactions are appropriately routed and processed by the relevant parts of the system.

A suitable programming language, such as NodeJS, will be used for the development of this module. Building on top of that, several technologies will be explored and finally be chosen to a) implement robust communication among the services (i.e., gRPC or custom logging/tracing mechanisms), b) efficiently monitor and secure such communication (i.e., Istio / Kuma, or encryption & validation mechanisms) and c) optimize the RESCALE deployment structure (i.e., Docker / Kubernetes integration)

Prerequisites & Dependencies

The component relies on the correct operation of both the analysis modules to provide the required input (SSCG/DSCG). Also, a functional dashboard interface that allows users to interact and apply different configurations within the system is required. Finally, a continuous connection to the RESCALE Communication Mechanism is required to allow seamless data & task-relevant information exchange between the rest of the modules. Thus, every RESCALE component must provide means and documentation regarding how required functional operations or execution environments can be monitored or accessed accordingly (e.g., infrastructure and network topology definition, available configurations, environment variables, micro-services used etc.).

Interaction & interfaces

The module communicates with static and dynamic analysis modules. It receives the SSCG, DSCG and guidelines from these analysis processes, using this information to inform subsequent actions and decisions within the system. Additionally, it can send commands or data requests to these analysis modules to initiate or modify analysis tasks as required. Data distribution is another critical interaction managed by the state management module. It provides trust-related data to TrustOR and receives feedback or requests for further information. For repositories, the module sends updated data and retrieves stored information as needed. Interaction with the blockchain involves submitting transactions and receiving confirmation and validation, ensuring the integrity of recorded TBOMs.

Moreover, it interferes with the dashboard, where it retrofits user inputs to meaningful RESCALE actions, so as to forward them to the corresponding components for further processing. In return, the State Management module provides feedback and updates to the user interface, reflecting the current state and actions taken within the system. The aforementioned interactions must include authentication tokens and relevant metadata (e.g., user's role, authentication certificates etc.), managed by the Communication Mechanisms and Auth/IAM modules.

The internal architecture of the State Management component is presented in figure 9 below.

Figure 9: RESCALE State Management

The input is received from the RESCALE Communication Mechanism component, utilizing the corresponding API endpoints from each component or deployed services relevant to network and services monitoring as described above. The input is then validated and authorized by the Authentication Service module to allow access control before it is forwarded for further filtering. Afterwards, the input is processed by internal scripts and services, while local configuration files and environmental variables persist in the internal storage of the component. Finally, the output containing the action to be performed or the response to a request (depending on the input) is being forwarded to the corresponding component by utilizing capabilities of the Communication Mechanism. The exact technologies and services that will be used will be defined and described towards the first prototype release of RESCALE.

3.3.2 Communication Mechanism

We foresee that the system characteristics of RESCALE and the nature of interactions between the various components will necessitate a robust infrastructure, to facilitate both synchronous and asynchronous communications. In response to this requirement, the utilization of a foundational component that will facilitate different types of communications emerges.

Table 17: Communication Mechanism - Component Information

Name: Communication Mechanism
Component Functional Description
<p>REST APIs will be a first-class citizen in the Communication Mechanism and will support direct and synchronous interactions. Components that require immediate communication will be able to send HTTP requests to the relevant API endpoints. Subsequently, the receiving component then processes these requests and provides the necessary responses. This facilitates necessary data exchange and command execution (e.g., triggering different RESCALE services, etc.). This synchronous interaction is particularly useful for operations requiring immediate feedback, such as updating user interfaces or executing critical transactions among the RESCALE platform.</p> <p>On the other hand, a message broker is well-suited for asynchronous communication patterns where the sender and receiver of a message do not need to interact with each other immediately. Including such a technology to the component will mainly cover asynchronous needs, but can also offer a solution for publish-subscribe cases, queues and RPCs. Message brokers are a natural fit for building event-driven architectures. This allows the different RESCALE components to integrate in a flexible way if/when needed (without direct coupling) and makes debugging across multiple abstractions easier. Message brokers also bring in the reliability and resilience of such technologies, by providing features like reliable message delivery, acknowledgements, message persistence and retry mechanisms, which can be beneficial for handling other component failures, potential network issues etc.</p>
Prerequisites & Dependencies
<p>The Communication Mechanism will be a vital part of the RESCALE platform. This means that selecting infrastructure / deployment options and setting up endpoints, topics, queues, exchanges, access control policies, message retention policies, and other configuration parameters based on the architecture's needs is among the initial steps of bootstrapping the whole platform.</p>
Interaction & Interfaces
<p>As it can easily be observed at the Reference Architecture figure 1, the Communication Mechanism acts as a central unit with most of RESCALE's components interfacing with it. This approach will let components communicate in a more direct way and alleviates the challenge of managing an extensive number of service-layers, which often leads to inefficient error propagation and cumbersome debugging processes. By providing a centralized point for communication, the debugging workflow is streamlined and more efficient.</p>

3.3.3 Auth / IAM

Table 18: Auth / IAM - Component Information

Name: Auth / IAM
Component Functional Description
<p>Auth/IAM will serve as the authentication and identity access management (IAM) component within the RESCALE platform. Its primary function is to handle user authentication, authorization, and identity-related tasks, ensuring secure access to the platform's resources and services. The component will provide identity and access management capabilities, utilize authentication protocols such as OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect, and allow users to authenticate via various methods.</p> <p>Auth/IAM is responsible for managing user identities, roles, and permissions, enforcing access control policies across different RESCALE components. It acts as a central identity provider, enabling secure and streamlined access to platform resources while maintaining compliance with security standards and regulations.</p>
Prerequisites & Dependencies
<p>Auth/IAM is one of the basic components and must be installed and configured early in the bootstrap process of the platform. It has to also be available and accessible by all the components that need authentication and authorization functionalities when running their tasks. Access policies based on user roles and permissions will have to be created. It is crucial for such a component to be deployed, configured and operated by following the appropriate security best practices.</p> <p>Finally, we are planning to explore open-source solutions/tools like Keycloak [13] for enhancing our authentication and identity management capabilities. With its versatility and extensive feature-set, Keycloak becomes a potential suitable choice for ensuring a smooth and reliable user authentication experience within the platform.</p>
Interaction & Interfaces
<p>RESCALE components that need authentication and authorization functionalities will have to integrate with Auth/IAM. User-interfaces like RESCALE Dashboard will be able to utilize the username/password login functionalities, other components which need programmatic access to services or resources will utilize the token issuance/token validation functionality.</p>

3.4 Trust Orchestrator

Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR) is the binding framework under which all different RESCALE components will be placed. It provides two main functionalities:

1. **Generating the RESCALE Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM)** for hardware and software, including all relevant reports.
2. **Validating an existing TBOM** to ensure its accuracy and security compliance.

TrustOR also communicates with a continuous security assessment mechanism, which is described in 3.7 Security Assurance to verify the currency of a TBOM. This mechanism monitors the security level of software in real-time, triggering the TBOM update process when new vulnerabilities are discovered.

3.4.1 TBOM Validator

Table 19: TBOM Validator - Component Information

Name: TBOM Validator
Component Functional Description
The TBOM Validator is responsible for ensuring that a TBOM is valid and up-to-date. It verifies the entries within the TBOM, ensuring compliance with current security standards and the integrity of the information.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ledger Adapter: Required to access and verify the entries recorded on the blockchain for each TBOM. • Security Assurance: Essential for assessing the current security status of the components listed in the TBOM.
Interaction & Interfaces
<p>The TBOM Validator interacts with various components to perform its functions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ledger Adapter: The TBOM Validator verifies all entries against the blockchain ledger to ensure their integrity and authenticity. • Security Assurance: It integrates with this platform to determine if a TBOM remains up-to-date from a security perspective, not just its validity. This ensures the TBOM reflects the latest security posture of the software components. • Repositories: When needed, it retrieves TBOMs and SSCG or DSCG reports from the equivalent repositories.

3.4.2 TBOM Generator

Table 20: TBOM Generator - Component Information

Name: TBOM Generator
Component Functional Description
The TBOM Generator is tasked with creating the TBOM for a software or hardware component within the RESCALE supply chain. More specifically, it combines the SSCG report generated by the Static Analysis Module and the DSCG report from the Dynamic Testing Module, to produce a comprehensive TBOM.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSCG and DSCG Repositories: To gather the necessary data for Static and Dynamic Supply chain Component Guarantees. • TBOM Repository: To securely store the results after generating a TBOM. • Specifications from Task 4.1: These specs guide the format and content of the TBOM.
Interaction & interfaces
<p>The TBOM Generator interfaces with several components to compile and verify the TBOM.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repositories: It collects SSCG/DSCG reports from the repositories to include them in the TBOM. After producing the TBOM, it also stores the generated result. • Ledger Interface: It communicates with the Ledger Interface to ensure the generated TBOM is secure and trustworthy. The Ledger Interface provides a tamper-proof record of the TBOM's contents, enhancing its credibility and integrity. • TBOM Generation Process: The DSCG Generator triggers the process of generating a new TBOM, so this component will provide a relative interface/endpoint for such tasks. Then the TBOM Generator proceeds by following the specifications provided by Task 4.1 to ensure that the generated TBOM adheres to the required standards and formats.

3.5 Repositories

Table 21: RESCALE Repositories - Component Information

Name: Repositories
Component Functional Description
Repositories serve as the storage and management component for storing critical artifacts and data within the RESCALE platform. It encompasses three distinct repositories, each dedicated to storing specific types of artifacts: SSCGs, DSCGs and TBOMs. This component will ensure the integrity, availability, and confidentiality of stored artifacts, implementing robust data management practices and security controls.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
Repositories will play a crucial role for the whole RESCALE platform since they will facilitate seamless retrieval, querying and potential manipulation of important artifacts (SSCGs & DSCGs) that contribute to the general end-goal, the generation of the Trusted Bills of Materials (TBOMs). Adequate infrastructure and choosing the appropriate databases to store the artifacts are necessary to support the deployment and operation of the SSCG, DSCG, and TBOM repositories.
Interaction & Interfaces
The State Management will be the main component that interacts with the repositories. This gives the appropriate control-level over something critical for the RESCALE platform. The Static Code Analysis and Dynamic Testing which produce the SSCG and DSCG reports respectively, will communicate their results to the State Management and the latter will store the artifacts to the repositories. Similarly, the TBOM Validator and Generator will also communicate via the State Management with the TBOM repository, since they are the components that deal with the TBOMs.

3.6 Trust Storage

The Trust Storage Module provides a trusted storage solution for the RESCALE project. It is divided into two primary components: the **Ledger Adapter** and the **Ledger Infrastructure**. The Ledger Adapter offers an interface for external users to interact with the module, while the Ledger Infrastructure houses the data and the trust anchor necessary to verify the integrity of this data. The Trust Storage Module is designed to be modular with respect to other modules and between its own components. This modular design allows flexibility and scalability within the RESCALE framework.

3.6.1 Ledger Adapter

Table 22: Ledger Adapter - Component Information

Name: Ledger Adapter
Component Functional Description
<p>The Ledger Adapter bridges the interaction between the RESCALE platform and the Ledger Infrastructure. This module serves as a client-side application that enables communication with the ledger API. For instance, a ledger adapter can be a programmatic client for a blockchain. Within the RESCALE platform, the Ledger Adapter ensures flexibility and seamless integration across diverse systems.</p> <p>The Ledger Adapter allows to convert the interface of the ledger API into an interface expected by the RESCALE platform, effectively translating requests and responses. This component isolates the RESCALE platform from any changes in the ledger API, making it easy to swap out or upgrade ledger systems without altering the core platform.</p>
Prerequisites & Dependencies
<p>For the Ledger Adapter to function, a Ledger Infrastructure must be in place for it to communicate with. Additionally, it depends on the operational status of relevant RESCALE components, such as TrustOR. These components generate the messages loaded into the Ledger Adapter to be sent to the blockchain, and the responses are routed back through this component into the RESCALE platform.</p>
Interaction & Interfaces
<p>The Ledger Adapter interacts directly with the underlying Ledger Infrastructure to gather data and integrity proofs. It also interacts with the RESCALE Management Module, which uses the adapter as an abstraction layer to access data and integrity proofs. The RESCALE TrustOR will use the management module to store, retrieve and preserve the integrity of the generated TBOMs. All communications between the Ledger Adapter and other components occur via REST API.</p>

The Ledger Adapter exposes APIs that interact with the underlying Ledger Infrastructure, providing a unified interface for managing data. This component includes functionalities for user management and TBOM management. A tentative list of API endpoints follows:

TBOM Management

- **POST /tboms** - Adds a new TBOM with details and dependencies.
- **PUT /tboms/tbomId** - Updates details and dependencies of an existing TBOM.
- **DELETE /tboms/tbomId** - Deletes an TBOM.
- **GET /tboms/tbomId** - Retrieves details and dependencies of an TBOM.
- **GET /tboms/tbomId/dependencies** - Lists dependencies of an TBOM.
- **POST /tboms/tbomId/verify** - Verifies the status of an TBOM.
- **POST /tboms/tbomId/outdate** - Marks an TBOM and its dependencies as outdated.

3.6.2 Ledger Infrastructure

Table 23: Ledger Infrastructure - Component Information

Name: Ledger Infrastructure
Component Functional Description
The Ledger Infrastructure defines a blockchain-based storage infrastructure to ensure the security and trustworthiness of TBOM data. It permits the verification of the authenticity of information while retaining accountability, liability, and non-reputability in a decentralized environment. This infrastructure stores information about the operations of the RESCALE framework and ensures their integrity. The infrastructure is divided into two layers: the Data Layer , where the data is actually stored and organized, and the Ledger Layer , where the integrity proofs are stored.
Prerequisites & Dependencies
To maintain integrity and safeguard trust, the Ledger Layer requires access to identity information of the participants and TBOM data. Prerequisites include the availability of deployment and development libraries for interacting with a blockchain solution. If using a self-deployed blockchain, nodes are required to deploy the blockchain. The Ledger Infrastructure exchanges with the ledger use a standardized interface to incentivize modularization. The Ledger Infrastructure interacts with the TrustOR to store and retrieve TBOM data through the standardized interface.
Interaction & Interfaces
The Ledger Infrastructure interacts with TrustOR and Auth/IAM through the Ledger Adapter and the Management Module. Communication occurs via REST APIs. The infrastructure ensures that all data interactions are secure and verifiable, maintaining a high level of trust and integrity within the RESCALE framework.

The Data Layer can utilize different types of storage solutions, such as SQL databases, NoSQL databases, and IPFS decentralized databases. While privacy concerns may dictate the choice of storage solution, the integrity of files is protected by the blockchain. The Ledger Layer can choose between different types of blockchains. Public blockchains like Ethereum and Cardano ease the burden of deployment but may impose costs that could be too high to support. Self-deployed solutions, such as Hyperledger Fabric, may constitute a cheaper alternative but would require the deployment of nodes and blockchain software.

The Ledger Layer will utilize smart contracts to manage the application logic, ensuring secure and automated handling of participants and TBOM data. Smart contracts will provide the necessary functionality for registering, updating, revoking, and querying information. A tentative template for the smart contracts follows:

TBOM Management Contract

- **register(string componentId, bytes32 tbomHash):** Registers the hash of an TBOM for a specific component.
- **update(string componentId, bytes32 newTbomHash):** Updates the hash of an TBOM for a specific component.

- **revoke(string componentId, bytes32 tbomHash):** Revokes a specific TBOM hash for a component.
- **verify(string componentId, bytes32 tbomHash) view returns (bool):** Verifies the integrity of an TBOM by comparing the given hash with the stored hash.
- **query(string componentId) view returns (TBOMRecord[]):** Retrieves the history of TBOM submissions for a component.

Data structures

- **struct Participant:** address participantAddress, string metadata.
- **struct TBOMRecord:** address participantAddress, string componentId, bytes32 tbomHash, uint256 timestamp.

3.7 Security Assurance

The Security Assurance Module is responsible for monitoring, testing, and assessing the security (& privacy, if needed) posture of the RESCALE project and their assets, in a real-time, continuous manner. Several built-in security assessments addressing the CIA principles (via custom metrics that can be tailored concerning the platform's components) can be utilized, leveraging an evidence-based approach, to provide security assurance assessments with certifiable results.

Table 24: Security Assurance - Component Information

Name: Security Assurance
Component Functional Description
This module will assess at run time whether a TBOM report about a software or hardware component remains current and valid against a rapidly changing vulnerabilities and fault discovery landscape. Once new vulnerabilities or security issues arise that have not been taken into consideration during the initial production of the TBOM, the Security Assurance will inform the TBOM Validator to trigger the TBOM update process and the end user with a notification (, etc.).
Prerequisites & Dependencies
Availability of TBOMs. Access to the National Vulnerability Database (NVD), a U.S. government repository of vulnerability management data maintained by the National Institute of Standards and Technology. In case where we want to secure the RESCALE platform, the Security Assurance platform will be connected to the different components of the system and place appropriate probes (e.g., elastic beats), providing RESCALE’s risk identification capabilities and orchestrating RESCALE’s continuous risk assessment capabilities. Monitoring the confidentiality of the RESCALE solution requires that security assurance can consume login logs from the respective components.
Interaction & Interfaces
The Security Assurance platform interacts with various components to perform its functions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TBOM Validator: The TBOM Validator invokes the Security Assurance platform for the assessment of a TBOM. • TBOM Repository: The Security Assurance platform retrieves the current and valid TBOMs from the TBOM repository for assessment. • TBOM Validator: If new vulnerabilities or security issues arise, the Security Assurance platform will inform the TBOM Validator to trigger a RESCALE TBOM update process. • Notification: Notify the end user if new vulnerabilities or security issues arise using email or a slack channel of the RESCALE dashboard.

3.8 Dashboard

The RESCALE Dashboard serves as the primary user interface of the system, aiming to provide an interactive and user-friendly graphical environment. The Dashboard will be developed as a role-based access web application and it will offer tailor-made screens and miscellaneous views, according to authorized end-users’ permission levels. The goal is to deliver a single access point for the security operators in order to inspect diverse RESCALE operations. The component mainly interacts with the State Management Module, in order to support heterogeneous user needs (e.g., user inputs digestion, data requests triggering, notification updates etc.). Finally, end-users will be able to monitor the progress statuses of ongoing Analysis operations (Static/Dynamic), inspect historical data on certification lifecycles and explore TBOM

associated details (e.g., generation and validation states, embedded metadata and more.)

Table 25: RESCALE Dashboard - Component Information

Name: Dashboard
Component Functional Description
<p>The RESCALE Dashboard serves as the primary user interface of the system. It will be developed by utilizing the capabilities of AEGIS Advanced Visualisation Toolkit (AVT). AVT provides user-friendly visualization dashboards that present multi-modal visual representations, combining data from different sources in both stream and batch formats. Through a widgets based orientation, it will support diverse user interactions, customized and comparison views, advanced filtering capabilities, while it will handle navigation options, user inputs absorption and tailor-made statistical portrayals.</p> <p>Moreover, AVT enables events exchange with interconnected back-end components or services. The RESCALE Dashboard will dynamically display information derived from the Management Module and user inputs. Such information refers to real-time updates regarding the operations of the static and dynamic analysis modules, historical information of previous certification lifecycles, current system status indicators and notifications, TBOMs details, security related findings, etc. The Dashboard will be a role-based access web application.</p>
Prerequisites & Dependencies
<p>Several prerequisites and dependencies need to be addressed to guarantee the effectiveness of the Dashboard component.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frontend Framework: A robust frontend framework (e.g. Angular) is required to build the user interface. • Middleware/Backend Services: Reliable client-side backend modules (e.g. Node.js) must be deployed to handle data transmission and support smooth interactions between users, front-end and back-end components. Part of these shall be managed by the State Management module. • API Endpoints: REST APIs and Web Sockets endpoints are necessary for communication between the dashboard and back end components. • Authentication & Authorization: A secure system for user authentication and authorization to ensure that only authorized users can access and interact with the web application. <p>In terms of deployment, AVT can either be fully installed as an application with moderate hardware and software requirements or can be executed as a containerized application with exposed configuration options and environment variables, allowing its smooth integration in existing environments.</p>
Interaction & Interfaces

The Dashboard communicates with back-end services through REST APIs and Web Socket endpoints. These interactions are used for fetching data, submitting user actions, and receiving responses, enabling synchronous communication for real-time data retrieval and action processing. For asynchronous communication, the Dashboard utilizes pub/sub protocols to subscribe to updates and notifications, allowing it to reflect real-time data changes instantly. In interaction with the State Management module, the Dashboard sends data requests to obtain specific information or trigger actions. This includes queries for system status, historical data, and analysis results. Furthermore, the Dashboard interferes with the Auth/IAM component to verify user credentials during login and manage user sessions. This integration ensures that only authorized users can interact with the system and access appropriate data, maintaining system security and integrity.

The internal architecture of the RESCALE Dashboard component is presented in figure 10 below.

Figure 10: RESCALE Dashboard

The user accesses and interacts (i.e., providing inputs / triggering functionalities) with the Dashboard through a web browser. The web application is developed based on an Angular Framework containing several open-source libraries. Multiple visualisation libraries and tailor-made services will offer a comprehensive RESCALE graphical user interface to fulfil end-users needs. Such services refer to access rights management, activity monitoring and more that are

implemented by executing Typescript written scripts. Configuration files and environmental variables, required for the RESCALE platform will be stored inside an internal resource directory for optimal retrieval and utilisation. Finally, different API gateways (e.g., HTTPs and Socket.IO clients) are deployed in order for the Dashboard to enable seamless communication with the Management Module and external back-end environments. Further details about concrete functionalities of the Dashboard will be reported towards the first prototype release of RESCALE.

4 Conclusion & Future Steps

4.1 Summary of Key Findings

In this deliverable, we have presented the first comprehensive version of the RESCALE high-level architecture, detailing its essential components, their functionalities, and their interactions.

The outlined architecture showcases all the critical components, namely: *Static Code Analysis, Dynamic Testing, Management Module, Trust Orchestrator, Dashboard, Trust Storage, Repositories, and Security Assurance*. Each component has been designed to address specific challenges within the supply chain, collectively ensuring the system's security, reliability, and efficiency. By leveraging advanced technologies and methodologies, the RESCALE platform will offer significant improvements in managing and validating software and hardware components across the supply chain.

This foundational work sets the stage for developing a robust platform aimed at enhancing supply chain security through advanced, modular solutions. The information documented in this deliverable will serve as the basis for effective communication and collaboration among technical partners and other relevant partners of the RESCALE project.

4.2 Recommendations for Project's Next Steps

To ensure the ongoing development and refinement of the RESCALE architecture, the following next steps will be undertaken:

- 1. Continuous Feedback from Work Package 2:** Task 2.2: Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification remains active and will continue to provide valuable insights and feedback to Task 2.3: High-Level Architecture Specification. This task has already influenced this deliverable through the detailed requirements outlined in Table 6 of D2.3. The final version of this analysis will be available in Month 21 with D2.4 - Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (final version), and will serve as a critical input for the second version of the RESCALE architecture, D2.6 - High Level Architecture (final version), scheduled for submission in Month 23. Additionally, it is important to note that T2.2 receives feedback from T2.1, where the specifications for the pilot use-cases are developed, and it undergoes a second cycle for refinements. These ongoing interactions within WP2 ensure that our architecture remains aligned with the latest technological advancements and project requirements.
- 2. Collaboration with Work Package 5:** With the recent commencement of WP5 - Integration, Deployment and Validation, a new feedback loop will be established. This work package will play a crucial role in validating the architecture through practical implementation and deployment, allowing us to refine and adjust the architecture based on real-world insights and performance data. This iterative process will help identify potential gaps and areas for improvement, ensuring the robustness and efficacy of the RESCALE platform.

3. **Stakeholder Engagement and Regulatory Compliance:** Ongoing engagement with stakeholders, including partners responsible for development work and industry partners who will demonstrate real use-case scenarios, will be essential to align RESCALE's advancements with market needs and regulatory standards. This engagement will facilitate the adoption of the platform and ensure that it meets both current and future demands in supply chain security.

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